

MARKET AND TRANSITIONAL MODELS OF INTERMEDIARY BEHAVIOR

Djambakieva Feruza Bakhtakhunovna

Lecturer of the Department of Private Law Sciences of the Specialized branch of the Tashkent State Law University

E-mail: dzhambakieva_feruza5@gmail.com

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Annotation. The article analyzes the institution of mediation — the basic component of the market economy. The scientific interpretation of classical (formed within the framework of developed economies) and transitional models of intermediary behavior is given, their classification is developed. The reasons and factors of inefficiency (cost) of the transactional sector of the modern world economy are investigated, which are caused by an institutional vacuum and a mismatch of formal and informal rules of behavior.

Key words: mediation, market economy, transactional sector, institutional vacuum, formal and informal rules of behavior.

A market economy is a social system of division of labor under conditions of private ownership of the means of production. All its participants act on their own behalf, but the actions of each of them, along with satisfying their own needs, are aimed at meeting the needs of other people. Acting, everyone renders services to the people around him and receives services from them. Everyone is both a means and an end in itself: the ultimate goal for themselves and a means for other people in their attempts to achieve their own goals. The market is neither a place, nor a thing, nor a collective entity. The market is a process set in motion by the interaction of many individuals cooperating in the conditions of division of labor. The forces that constantly change and determine the state of the market are subjective assessments of individuals and their actions, controlled by these subjective assessments. The state of the market at any given time is represented by the price structure, i.e. a set of exchange coefficients established as a result of the interaction of those who seek to buy and those who seek to sell. There is nothing mystical and uncharacteristic about the market. The market process is entirely the resultant of human actions. The reason for any market phenomenon can be found in a specific choice made by members of the market community. An important feature of the market is the system of social cooperation (partnership), which arises in the process of complementary exchange of economic values between people pursuing their individual goals. The system of division of labor and the corresponding system of market

exchange specializes economic agents, diversifying their relations in a huge range of values. Thus, economic agents operating in various sectors of the economy and in a complementary exchange relationship with each other are objectively interested in maintaining dynamic equilibrium in the process of redistribution of benefits and costs between them. This applies to all market agents who are "on different sides" of supply and demand, including employees and employers, lenders and borrowers, producers and consumers, tenants and landlords, sellers and buyers, etc.

It should be noted that the supply and demand relations that connect economic agents are only the final phase of their contract-interactive interaction associated with the transfer of ownership rights to the goods and services exchanged. This external (empirical) shell of the market, which is the most obvious and tangible, hides a multilevel system of discrete chains of economic exchange. They are stretched over huge "distances", transmitting economic values from one agent to another. In this context, all subjects of economic behavior (regardless of their status and specialization) are transfer (transit) links in an infinite network of economic exchange. Within its framework, each subject, pursuing their personal interests, tries to optimize them in the process of price adjustment to the conjuncture of supply and demand, exchanging economic values with their own kind. On this basis, a complex system of exchange of values is structured, the main trend of development of which is based on ensuring stable, long-term and guaranteed connections between the majority of market agents. The latter can optimize their economic interest mainly under the condition of redistribution of marginal benefits and costs between their partners. One of the important components of mutually beneficial interaction and coordination of marginal norms of substitution of goods between economic agents is the exchange of information between them. This is primarily due to the fact that the market system of free and compensated exchange of information is a prerequisite for all maximizing actions aimed at obtaining benefits. Firstly, we are talking about the fact that all agents of economic exchange, regardless of their specialization, are sources of information for each other (primarily price). Secondly, the information field of economic exchange that they use does not exist in some abstract form, but is scattered discretely and is the personal and confidential property (property) of each of them. Thirdly, information is provided to others only in cases when it is exchanged in a complementary way, or in cases of its direct purchase and sale at a certain price, since information is a commodity. Based on this, it can be

concluded that all subjects of economic exchange in one form or another (degree) perform intermediary functions in relation to each other, i.e. they are sources of knowledge for other market partners. This knowledge is transmitted through the chains of economic exchange, constantly reducing the costs of information retrieval and increasing its efficiency. Thus, mediation in its various specialized (professional and non-professional) forms is an immanent property of market behavior, an objective function of everyone who enters into market exchange, regardless of whether he is aware of it or not. This is a universal institutional factor of economic exchange, without which the latter is simply impossible. It should be noted that market exchange in the modern economy is activated by many intermediaries. They construct communicative, institutional, regulatory, informational, social and other mechanisms (channels) that simplify, expand and accelerate the communication between sellers and buyers in various sectors of the economy. Mediation theory is being productively developed in sociology within the framework of the theory of social networks for the study of various components of modern society. The analysis of social networks is differentiated into many areas and specializations. The subject of this theory is many social phenomena, starting with the study of traditional societies, the family and ending with such sociological problems as the study of labor markets, commercial and consumer behavior, consumer and financial "communities", professional careers, criminal behavior, etc.

It seems that social networks are a conceptual and empirical specification of the theory of social exchange. The latter proceeds from the fact that the phenomenon of social (economic) exchange itself is not realized at a purely interactive level. It takes place in various social and institutional contexts, which determine the most diverse orders of social interaction, regulating social contacts and directions of social communication between individuals and groups. According to the theory of social networks, the most important factor of social communication and interaction are social intermediaries of various specialization and functions. They operate at different levels of the social system, including economic, stratification, ethnic, settlement, regional, political, clan, etc. Through social networks, each of which is a communication system of strongly and weakly integrated communities (large and small), there is a movement of information and various signals of social mobility. In the structure of these networks, cells of "special influence" are formed, the places in which are occupied by so-called social intermediaries. They have different statuses and

functions, but their main task is to ensure social ties, communications between members of various communities both within them and between them.

We identify such criteria as the depth of mediation functions and their specialization as the main parameters of the classification of mediation activities. The depth of mediation should be understood as the degree of penetration of the intermediary into the operational and economic activities of his clients. When we talk about the "depth" of intermediary functions, we mean the institutional conditions that have developed in the process of social evolution of the market and codified in various legal systems regulating the behavior of economic agents. We are talking about the institutional framework of economic actions that have certain specifics and are reflected in various models of intermediary behavior. Before highlighting the "institutional stages" and the models of mediation behavior corresponding to them, which characterize the "depth" of mediation functions, it should be noted that various mediation institutions in various legislations and legal literature are evaluated and interpreted differently. For example, in some legal systems the category "agent" is defined specifically and has a regulatory justification, in others it is not. A broker can be understood as an intermediary who is authorized to conclude transactions on behalf of, on behalf of and at the expense of his client, but can also act on his own behalf. These discrepancies, which sometimes exist even within the same legal system, are due to the fact that intermediaries can perform many functions related to securing their clients' transactions and specialize accordingly. Therefore, the institutional stages of mediation proposed by us are largely hypothetical.

The first institutional stage of a transaction (transaction) between two parties with the help of a third party is the transfer of information about the place. the location ("address") of economic agents who need each other's services. This information includes various information about their economic parameters and the field of activity in which they specialize. At the same time, the intermediary does not know about the specific intentions of its clients regarding the transaction. His task is to give the necessary information to everyone who needs it. Intermediaries of this kind — advertising agents and agencies, demonstrating an information and communication model of behavior, use various media and various technologies of its presentation and distribution in order to attract mass interest in the products and services of their customers, with whom they (intermediaries) work on a paid commercial basis. In modern market conditions, advertising firms are powerful economic structures covering a huge

number of market agents. However, they cannot fully display the huge amount of information that is being circulated on the market. Therefore, there is a rather narrow specialization in the information and advertising sector, which is constantly deepening. Thus, the provision of transactions at this level consists in the implementation of a simple "impersonal" contract or a simple purchase and sale transaction, which is carried out in the information services market. Here, information intermediaries, transmitting information about potential participants in transactions (on the supply or demand side), are essentially anonymous for their clients. They have only one-sided information, having no information about the specific interactions of the parties.

The second institutional stage of the transaction between the two parties with the help of a third party. In contrast to the intermediaries of the first stage, whose functions are limited only to the supply of information about the potential supply and demand for various goods and services, intermediaries included in the second institutional stage of the organization of transactions in the market have direct contact with potential participants in transactions. At this level, one of the most ancient and massive (classical) categories of intermediaries implementing the broker's model of behavior is concentrated. They bring the interested parties together, can, if necessary, participate in negotiations as consultants, but the decision to conclude a deal is made by their clients. The main specificity of the activity of intermediaries of this kind (brokers) is that they, carrying out (absorbing) the information function, constantly search for counterparties who are interested in specific transactions. At the same time, the search is carried out simultaneously by contractors. This significantly accelerates the process of formation of new transactions, which intensifies the turnover of economic resources, reducing the costs of the parties and increasing the effectiveness of their actions. One very important function of this category as intermediaries should be noted. Numerous facts of opportunistic behavior of various parties to transactions have led to the fact that most intermediaries of this kind explicitly or not explicitly have to provide guarantees of reliability of partners entering into economic exchange. Ultimately, we are talking about the reputation of an intermediary who, by constructing dubious transactions, may lose his clients in the future. Factors of maintaining trust, reliability and reputation contributed to the emergence of additional services in the activities of "irresponsible" intermediaries. They are known as "business-to-business" services, i.e. services for providing and verifying confidential information about the activities of potential

counterparties of the transaction. Another important feature of the intermediaries of the second stage is the discreteness of their relations with their clients. The intermediary (broker) contract is not a long-term agreement and assumes only one-time obligations of the parties, which are terminated after the conclusion of the main contract. Thus, in terms of second-stage contracts, intermediaries are autonomous agents of the market, without binding themselves to long-term obligations with their clients.

The third institutional stage of a transaction between two parties with the help of a third party. Intermediaries of this stage — representatives are in direct contact with their clients and in one way or another facilitate the process of concluding a transaction between them. The main feature of representative behavior is that its subjects facilitate the conclusion of a transaction as proxies. They can also contribute to an already concluded transaction by being participants in a specific transaction. Thus, unlike the intermediaries of the second stage, they directly replace the specific functions of their clients and are in a relatively long and trusting relationship with them. On behalf of their clients, representatives search for counterparties and select possible counterparties, collect the necessary information about them, conduct preliminary and basic negotiations. However, taking an active part in the process of concluding a transaction, they are not responsible for the consequences of its conclusion and do not have rights and access to the resources (goods, money) of their clients. We repeat that, with all the variety of functions of third-stage intermediaries and the degree of their participation in the operational and economic activities of their clients (including actions "inside" specific transactions that they contributed to), they are not the owners of the resources entrusted to them. That is, the orders that are given to the intermediary by the client do not cancel the full ownership of the latter over its resources. The fourth institutional stage of making a transaction between two parties with the help of a third person. This type of mediation involves an even deeper involvement of the intermediary in the operational and economic activities of its clients. The range of functions of the intermediary is further expanded, which increases the degree of interdependence between him and his clients. Intermediaries of this kind — attorneys — are transferred not only the trust rights to execute orders, but also the ownership rights to the transaction resources from the client. Moreover, the client loses these rights until the expiration of the order. The process of delegating property rights, their redistribution between the intermediary and his clients is characterized by the following features. Firstly, the attorneys get

the full right to conclude transactions on behalf of their clients. Secondly, in addition to concluding a contract, if necessary, at their own risk, they can perform other appropriate actions to optimize the transaction.

Thirdly, the attorneys. they are confidential representatives (partners) of their clients who are excluded from the process of managing commodity flows for the duration of the order. Fourth, the intermediary can independently make payments on his client's obligations, maintain his accounts, and carry out other financial transactions. Thus, at this level, the institution of mediation is a structure of "higher trust", and the intermediary is directly involved in the transaction constructed by him and is deeply embedded in the operational and economic activities of his client. If there is no trust between the intermediary and the client, then intermediary operations of this kind become meaningless, since the intermediary, having confidential information about the activities of his client, can use them to his advantage.

The fifth institutional stage of a transaction between two parties with the help of a third party is characterized by an even greater redistribution of property rights between intermediaries and their clients. The intermediary of the fifth stage — the commission agent — can conclude transactions on behalf of his clients (committees), but already on his own behalf. In addition, he acquires the right to dispose of the economic resources (goods) of his clients, being responsible for the results of the transaction not only to them, but also to third parties. The most important thing in the diversification of property rights between the commission agent and his client is that the former becomes a party to the transaction, and his client may not appear in the contract with a third party at all. If in previous cases the intermediaries were autonomous or relatively autonomous agents of the market, not responsible for the consequences of their actions, or

when executing orders under the control of the client, the commission agent, being a full party to the transaction, performs a number of lengthy and confidential operations instead of the committee. For example, a commission agent may be the manager of his client's goods in the interests of the latter, but independently carry out transactions with third parties, as well as be responsible for the preservation of goods during various trading operations. Being responsible for the implementation of the transaction on the obligations of his client and a third party, the intermediary-commission agent bears much higher costs than simple intermediaries who only bring clients together to conclude a transaction. And since the commission agent's risk increases, then

the share of his remuneration should be much higher. Mediation of this kind is necessary in many cases, for example, related to the client's uncertainty in the market, the promotion of which he trusts an economic agent with extensive professional experience and a solid reputation. Another possible reason is the closure of the market for a client who trusts his intermediary who has access to him to conduct trading operations. Thus, one of the important functions of an intermediary-commission agent is that, as a rule, having a solid reputation in the market, he can completely replace his client, keeping him incognito.

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